

NOTATKA / NOTE

New records of alien beetle species (Insecta: Coleoptera) in southern Poland

Nowe stwierdzenia obcych gatunków chrząszczy (Insecta: Coleoptera) w południowej Polsce

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ABSTRACT. New data on new findings of eight alien beetle species in Poland are presented with the first case of introduction of *Trogoxylon aequale*.

KEY WORDS: *Lyctus africanus*, *Trogoxylon aequale*, *Cryptolestes pusillus*, *Cryptolestes turcicus*, *Epuraea ocularis*, *Cynaenus angustus*, *Gnathotrichus materiarius*, *Xyleborinus attenuatus*.

In the last few decades, we have been increasingly dealing with cases of insects from various orders, including beetles, being introduced to Europe, including Poland (e.g. RABITSCH 2008, ROQUES et al. 2009, COEUR D'ACIER 2010, DENUX, ZAGATTI 2010, LOPEZ-VAAMONDE et al. 2010, RASPLUS et al. 2010, SKUHRAVÁ et al. 2010, YUS-RAMOS et al. 2014, KATSANEVAKIS et al. 2015, JELÍNEK et al. 2016, MOKRZYCKI 2016, BIENKOWSKI & ORLOVA-BIENKOWSKAJA 2018, OLENICI et al. 2022). Species that can adapt to climatic conditions often spread to new areas without encountering resistance from biotic environmental factors. Some of them are or may be harmful to the human economy in the future, such as *Anoplophora glabripennis* (MOTSCH.), *Diabrotica virgifera* LE CONTE, *Xylosandrus germanus* (BLDF.) (Coleoptera), *Hyphantria cunea* (DRURY) (Lepidoptera), *Dreyfusia nordmanniana* (ECKST.), *Halyomorpha halys* (STÅL) (Hemiptera), *Obolodiplosis robiniae* (HALD.) (Diptera), and many others (ROY et al. 2019, HAUBROCK et al. 2021). Others, originating mainly from tropical regions, are found incidentally, with no chance for further development, unless in heated conditions, as elements of synanthropic fauna (DOMINIK 1983).

Information on new records of eight alien beetle species from different families is given below. One species was introduced for the first time to Poland, the rest were recorded earlier from the country at different periods, but a large number of them in the last ten years.

Bostrichidae

Lyctus africanus LESNE, 1907 – Kraków-Wieluń Upland: DA24 Kraków, V 2014 – I 2015, 20 exx., hatched from a rattan basket purchased from an African handicraft shop in Kraków; M. BUJOCZEK & T. WOJAS leg., T. WOJAS det. et coll.

Species native to the African continent and southwestern Asia, occasionally brought to various regions of the world with wood and wood products made of various deciduous species (BOROWSKI & WĘGRZYNOWICZ 2007). Due to environmental requirements, it cannot develop in the climate conditions of Central Europe. From Poland, so far reported from Żory (Upper Silesia), where it was recorded in 2005 (SZOŁTYS & GRZYWOCZ 2014).

Trogoxylon aequale (WOLLASTON, 1867) – Kraków-Wieluń Upland: DA13 Kraków-Sidzina, 1-10 XI 2022, 5 exx., hatched from wooden elements of a handicraft called a “dream catcher”, brought from Mexico (Yucatan Peninsula); MG leg., T. WOJAS det. et coll.

Species inhabiting Central America and Brazil, occasionally brought to other regions of the world, including Europe (BOROWSKI & WĘGRZYNOWICZ 2007). It damages the wood of various deciduous species, preferring leguminous wood (LIU & GEIS 2019). It is the first documented case of this species being introduced to Poland. In our conditions, it is unable to develop outside heated spaces.

Laemophloeidae

Cryptolestes pusillus (SCHÖNHERR, 1817) – Kraków-Wieluń Upland: DA24 Kraków-Śródmieście, 13 II 2025, 1 ex., in the apartment; leg., det. et coll. T. WOJAS.

A cosmopolitan species of unknown region of origin, considered a locally important pest of stored plant products, mainly grains of various cereals (HALSTEAD 1993). In Poland, known from ten localities, mostly located in large cities (RUTA et al. 2023, Mapa bioróżnorodności). The record in Kraków is also first for the Kraków-Wieluń Upland.

Cryptolestes turcicus (GROUVELLE, 1876) – Kraków-Wieluń Upland: DA24 Kraków-Śródmieście, 1 XII 2007, several dozen exx. collected in a jar of wholemeal rye flour, purchased at the city market; leg., det. et coll. T. WOJAS.

Like the previous one, it is a pest of plant products, widely distributed in the world (outside Australia and SE Asia), but preferring ground grain (HALSTEAD 1993). From Poland reported over 60 years ago from three sites located in cities (Boguszów-Gorce, Gdańsk, Wrocław) (BURAKOWSKI et al. 1986). It was not yet recorded from Kraków – new for the Kraków-Wieluń Upland.

Nitidulidae

Epuraea ocularis FAIRMAIRE, 1849 – Małopolska Upland: DA34 Kraków-Bieńczyce, 12 IX 2024, several dozen exx., in a garden, on fallen, rotting apples; Kraków-Wieluń Upland: DA24 Kraków-Śródmieście, 10 VIII 2024, 8 exx., 12 VIII 2024, 23 exx., in compost, on banana peels; leg., det. et coll. T. WOJAS.

Species originating from East Asia, introduced in the 1990s to the Canary Islands and Madeira, from where it spread through southwestern Europe to Southern and Central Europe, Asia Minor and the Caucasus (JELÍNEK et al. 2016). In Poland, it was recorded for the first time in several locations in Upper Silesia in the years 2022-2023 (LASONI et al. 2023). Numerous occurrences in various locations in Kraków indicate the expansion of the species in the southern part of the country.

Tenebrionidae

Cynaesus angustus (LECONTE, 1851) – Lower Silesia: BA99 Góra św. Anny, Krępa Forest Range, comp. 644i, 25 V 2024, 7 exx., in an oak-hornbeam forest, on a lying log of silver birch *Betula pendula* ROTH, on polypores; leg., det. et coll. T. WOJAS.

Species native to northern Mexico and the southwestern part of the USA, from where it first spread to the central states of the USA, and later

introduced to Europe in the 1960s. Observed mainly in synanthropic biotopes, in plant waste, less frequently found in natural biotopes (DUNKEL et al. 1982, KOVALENKO et al. 2016). In Poland, discovered in Trzebnica Hills (Oborniki Śląskie), in a forest under the bark of a dead beech in 2015 (RUTA et al. 2017). The current location was also in a forest biotope, about 120 km southeast of the above-mentioned one.

Curculionidae

Gnathotrichus materiarius (FITCH, 1858) – Sandomierz Lowland: DA54 Niepołomice Forest, Hysne Forest Range, comp. 125, 23 IV 2023, 1 ex., on felled Scots pine logs; Kraków-Wieluń Upland: DA04 Brodła Forest Range, comp. 329, 3 VI 2024, 2 exx., on felled Scots pine log; leg., det. et coll. T. WOJAS.

Introduced from North America to Europe (France) almost a hundred years ago, but only recently settled in Central European countries – in Poland it was discovered in the southwestern part of the country, in the Kamienna Góra Forest District near Wałbrzych in 2015 (MOKRZYCKI 2016). It inhabits various species of coniferous trees. In Poland, it was found in several locations in Lower and Upper Silesia (SZOŁTYS et al. 2019). Current occurrences indicate further spread of the species towards the east.

Xyleborinus attenuatus (BLANDFORD, 1894) – Sandomierz Lowland: DA53 Niepołomice Forest, Kłaj Forest Range, 10 IV 2009, 1 ex., K. SOBOLAK leg.; Kraków-Wieluń Upland: DA13 Kraków-Podgórze Tynieckie, 18 III 2012, 2 exx., in an oak-hornbeam forest, on the trunk of hornbeam; Kraków-Wieluń Upland: CA95 Dulowa Forest Range, comp.107, 15 X 2017, 2 exx., in logs of black alder; leg., det. et coll. T. WOJAS.

Species originating from East Asia, introduced to Europe in the 1980s, as well as to Canada and the USA (MOKRZYCKI 2016). Ambrosia bark beetle, found in the wood of various species of deciduous trees. In Poland, it has been found in several locations in the southern, central and eastern part of the country (MOKRZYCKI et al. 2011). It has not been reported so far from either the Sandomierz Lowland or the Kraków-Wieluń Upland.

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